

THE ROLE OF GENDER IN THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN TRUST AND ADVERTISING AVOIDANCE ON INSTAGRAM: AN EMPIRICAL STUDY OF MOROCCAN USERS

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Abstract: Gender is an important variable in the analysis of digital behaviors, as several studies show that men and women may differ in their perceptions of technologies, their assessment of risks related to personal data usage, and their level of online trust (Sánchez-Franco, 2006; Awad & Ragowsky, 2008; Park, 2015). At the same time, social media advertising has become a central component of corporate communication strategies, particularly on platforms such as Instagram where promotional content is directly integrated into users' browsing environments. In this context, gender differences may also influence how users react to advertising content embedded within digital platforms.

Moreover, trust in the use of personal data appears to be a key factor that may affect users' acceptance or rejection of data-driven advertising practices (Culnan & Armstrong, 1999; Dinev & Hart, 2006; Bleier & Eisenbeiss, 2015).

From this perspective, the present study examines the role of gender in the relationship between trust in the use of personal data and advertising avoidance behaviors on Instagram. A quantitative survey was conducted among 186 Moroccan Instagram users using a self-administered online questionnaire. The data were analyzed using Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM), complemented by a multi-group analysis.

The results show that trust has a negative effect on advertising avoidance, both at the cognitive and behavioral levels. However, these relationships are not statistically significant. The multi-group analysis also indicates that the differences observed between men and women remain weak and non-significant. These findings suggest that, in the studied context, gender does not significantly modify the effect of trust in personal data usage on advertising avoidance behaviors on Instagram, highlighting that other factors may play a more important role in shaping users' responses to digital advertising.

Keywords : Trust; Advertising avoidance; Gender; Instagram; Personal data.